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Multi Threshold Segmentation Approach Based on Ageist Spider Monkey Optimization Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

Image segmentation remains a prominent research area, with multi-level thresholding being a current focus of study. Histogram-based methods are often utilized for automatic threshold detection in this context. In this research, a histogram-based approach for bi-modal and multi-modal segmentation of grayscale images is proposed, utilizing the Ageist Spider Monkey Optimization algorithm (ASMO) algorithm. ASMO is employed to optimize Kapur's and Otsu's objective functions. Standard test images data are used to evaluate the performance of the ASMO algorithm, and results are compared against benchmarks established by the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm. The findings indicate that the new segmentation method outperforms PSO in terms of optimal threshold values and processing time (CPU).

Keywords: Image segmentation, Thresholding, Ageist Spider Monkey Optimization algorithm (ASMO).

1. Introduction

Image segmentation is a crucial technique in advanced image analysis. It typically involves dividing an image into meaningful sections or regions, where each region consists of pixels or voxels and their relationships with various data feature values. Image segmentation has numerous applications, including medical imaging [1, 2], object recognition, machine vision, object detection, and quality inspection of materials [3, 4].

Image segmentation can be done in a number of ways, such as region-based approaches [5], threshold-based approaches, and edge detection. Among these, threshold-based segmentation stands out as a simple yet effective method. This approach can be categorized into two types: bi-level (modal) and multi-level (model) segmentation. In bi-level segmentation, one threshold value is selected to divide the image into two groups. However, in real-world scenarios, image histograms are typically multi-level, making it challenging to accurately identify the positions of valleys in multi-modal histograms. As a result, Research on multi-modal thresholding has grown to be both fascinating and significant.

In recent decades, numerous thresholding techniques have been put out [6, 7]. A comprehensive survey of these methods highlights a wide range of approaches [6, 7],

encompassing both local and global thresholding approaches, with global histogram-dependent approaches being a popular choice for threshold determination [8, 9]. Two further categories of global thresholding techniques are point-dependent [7] and region-dependent. The grey level dispersion of each class is taken to have a normal distribution in point-dependent approaches. These techniques, however, are frequently computationally demanding.

Otsu's technique [10] maximizes the variance between grey levels of several classes to determine the ideal threshold, whereas Kapur's approach [11] maximizes the entropy of the histogram to get an ideal threshold. Even though both approaches have been expanded to multi-level thresholding, the exponential rise in processing time causes them to struggle in determining the ideal threshold values. To address this issue, various methods have been developed to solve the multi-modal thresholding problem. Evolutionary algorithms, such as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [12], are commonly used to select multi-modal thresholds and reduce computational time.

Ageist Spider Monkey Optimization algorithm (ASMO) [13], first introduced by Siddhartha Bhattacharyya et al., is a modern optimizing algorithm influenced by how spider monkeys forage for food. These creatures are categorized as belonging to a fission-fusion social hierarchy. In this work, multi-modal threshold values for picture segmentation are chosen using the ASMO method. The ASMO technique is evaluated on a range of photos, and its effectiveness is contrasted with Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) concerning CPU processing time and ideal threshold values.

2. Threshold based Problem statement

The best methods for multi-thresholding choose threshold values such that the image histogram's different classes satisfy predetermined requirements. This is accomplished by using the chosen thresholds as parameters in an optimization process that maximizes or minimizes an objective function. Two well-known thresholding techniques are used in this paper: the first, by Kapur et al., thresholds the data using the entropy of the histogram, and the second, by Otsu, thresholds the data using the grey level histogram.

The following is a description of a novel bi-modal or bi-level thresholding algorithm that Kapur introduced [11]: Let G_L represent the gray levels in a given image, with the range of gray levels being $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, (G_L - 1)\}$. The probability of occurrence of a gray level l is defined by the following equation:

$$F_l = \frac{k(l)}{N} \quad \text{for } (0 \leq l \leq (G_L - 1)),$$

Where M represents the total number of pixels in the image and is alternatively expressed as $M = \sum_{l=0}^{G_L-1} k(l)$ and where $k(l)$ indicates the number of pixels for the matching grey level G_L . Then, as stated below, the goal is to maximize the fitness function:

$$OF(s) = K_0 + K_1, \tag{1}$$

Where

$$K_0 = - \sum_{l=0}^{s-1} \frac{F_l}{v_0} \ln \frac{F_l}{v_0}, \quad v_0 = \sum_{l=0}^{s-1} F_l \text{ and}$$

$$K_1 = - \sum_{l=s}^{G_L-1} \frac{F_l}{v_1} \ln \frac{F_l}{v_1}, \quad v_1 = \sum_{l=s}^{G_L-1} F_l$$

The following can be used to characterize the shortcoming of above Kapur's entropy of histogram methodology, which also extends to multi-modal thresholding or multi-level thresholding: m-dimensional optimisation problem, where the goal is to maximise the objective function, for a given image $[s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots, s_m]$, selecting the m optimal threshold values:

$$Of([s_1, s_2, s_3, \dots, s_m]) = K_0 + K_1 + K_2 + \dots K_m \quad (2)$$

$$K_0 = - \sum_{l=0}^{s_1-1} \frac{F_l}{v_0} \ln \frac{F_l}{v_0}, \quad v_0 = \sum_{l=0}^{s_1-1} F_l \text{ and}$$

$$K_1 = - \sum_{l=s_1}^{s_2-1} \frac{F_l}{v_1} \ln \frac{F_l}{v_1}, \quad v_1 = \sum_{l=s_1}^{s_2-1} F_l \text{ and}$$

$$K_2 = - \sum_{l=s_2}^{s_3-1} \frac{F_l}{v_2} \ln \frac{F_l}{v_2}, \quad v_2 = \sum_{l=s_2}^{s_3-1} F_l \quad \text{and}$$

$$K_m = - \sum_{l=s_n}^{G_L-1} \frac{F_l}{v_n} \ln \frac{F_l}{v_n}, \quad v_n = \sum_{l=s_n}^{G_L-1} F_l$$

Otsu created the following threshold-value determination technique [10], which is based on between-class variance: X_l represents the pixels at grey level G_L , and $(X_1 + X_2 + \dots + X_{G_L})$ is the total number of pixels, or N. The following is the definition of the probability of occurrence at the l th grey level:

$$P_l = \frac{X_l}{N}, \quad P_l \geq 0, \quad \sum_{l=1}^{G_L} P_l = 1.$$

An image is divided into two classes, C_0 and C_1 , if it is bi-level, at threshold level s , The grey levels in class C_0 are from 0 to s , and the grey levels in class C_1 are from $s + 1$ to L , and the

following describes the distribution of the grey level probabilities ($v_0(s)$ and $v_1(s)$) for the two classes:

$$C_0: \frac{P_1}{v_0(s)}, \dots, \frac{P_s}{v_0(s)},$$

And

$$C_1: \frac{P_{s+1}}{v_1(s)}, \dots, \frac{P_L}{v_1(s)},$$

Where $v_0(s) = \sum_{l=1}^s P_l$ and $v_1(s) = \sum_{l=s+1}^{G_L} P_l$.

Mean values of C_0 and C_1 classes are m_0 and m_1 ; respectively, and explain in the following manner:

$$m_0 = \sum_{l=1}^s \frac{lp_l}{v_0(s)},$$

$$m_1 = \sum_{l=s+1}^{G_L} \frac{lp_l}{v_1(s)}.$$

It is simple to demonstrate that if the image's mean intensity is m_s .

$$v_0 m_0 + v_1 m_1 = m_s, \text{ and } v_0 + v_1 = 1.$$

Based on analysis, the level's total variance is:

$$\tau_{BC}^2 = \tau_0 + \tau_1$$

Here $\tau_0 = v(m_0 - m_s)^2$ and $\tau_1 = v_1(m_1 - m_s)^2$.

We can define the objective function as follows:

$$\text{maximize } J(s) = \tau_{BC}^2 = \tau_0 + \tau_1. \quad (3)$$

The aforementioned technique can be expanded to address multi-modal thresholding issues [8] and is explained as follows: m-dimensional improvement drawback: for a given image $[s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n]$, determine the n optimal threshold values that separate the original image into n categories such as C_0 for $[0, \dots, s_1 - 1]$, C_0 for $[s_1, \dots, s_2 - 1]$... and C_n for $[s_n, \dots, G_L - 1]$, and the best threshold values are selected by maximizing the following equation:

$$\text{maximize } J(s) = \tau_0 + \tau_1 + \dots + \tau_n, \quad (4)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned}\tau_0 &= v_0(m_0 - m_s)^2, \\ \tau_1 &= v(m_1 - m_s)^2, \\ \tau_2 &= v(m_2 - m_s)^2, \\ &\text{and so on} \\ \tau_n &= v(m_n - m_s)^2\end{aligned}$$

This research utilizes the ASMO technique to maximize the target objective of both Otsu's and Kapur's multi-modal thresholding methodologies in order to find the optimal threshold values.

Overview of Ageist Spider Monkey Optimization algorithm

In the category of swarm intelligence, the Ageist spider monkey optimization method [12] is the most recent development. The intelligent foraging behavior of fission-fusion social structure organisms serves as the motivation for ASMO [13-15].

Step 1. Initialize the Parameters:

Set up the groups and variables. Define the total number of major groups (MG), and for each major group, have subgroups (mini-groups).

Step 2. Loop through Major Groups:

For each major group k where $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, MG\}$:

Proceed to loop through each mini-group within that major group.

Step 3. Loop through Mini-Groups:

For each mini-group m where $m \in \{1, 2\}$:

Loop through each member SM_{mi} of the mini-group m .

Step 4. Loop through Decision Variables:

For each decision variable $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, D\}$:

Check a condition based on a probability value $R(p)$ with respect to a random threshold r_u where $(p) \geq r_u$.

Step 5. Update Member's Position:

If the condition in step 4 holds:

Update the position of member SM_{ij} in the mini-group based on the equation:
 $SM_{ij}^{new} = SM_{ij} + R(p) \times (SM_{kj} - SM_{ij}) + (1 - r_u) \times (SM_{rj} - SM_{ij})$

Here, SM_{kj} and SM_{rj} represent other members in the group, $R(p)$ and r_u are random values.

Step 6. Loop through Mini-Group Members:

After updating all positions, for each member SM_{mi} in the mini-group:

Step 7. Calculate New Fitness:

Calculate the new fitness value $fitness_i^{new}$ for member SM_{mi} .

Step 8. Fitness Comparison:

If the new fitness $fitness_i^{new}$ is better than the current $fitness_i$ then:

Step 9. Update Position and Fitness:

For each decision variable $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, D\}$:

Update the member's position SM_{ij} with the new position: $SM_{ij} = SM_{ij}^{new}$

Update the fitness value:

$$fitness_i = fitness_i^{new}$$

4. Result and Discussions

Using five typical test images, the applicability and efficacy of the previously discussed method for multi-level thresholding in image segmentation are assessed. The results obtained through the ASMO (Ageist Spider Monkey Optimization algorithm) approach are compared with those from the PSO (Particle Swarm Optimization) technique. The parameters for the ASMO algorithm are listed in Table 1.

The suggested method is used to calculate the entropy of Kapur's extended function, a histogram-based objective function, and is contrasted with the PSO methodology. The objective values, ideal thresholds, and CPU times are shown in Table 2. The PSO methodology is not as effective as the suggested strategy. When $n = 5$ is used instead of alternative values of n , the segmentation quality for all five test photos is better.

Table 1 Parameter used in ASMO method

Parameter	Value
Population size	50
Maximum Number of Groups MG	5
GL_{limit}	2000
LL_{limit}	0.2-0.5

Table 2 Comparison when utilizing Kapur's objective function

Test images	n	Objective Values		Threshold value		CPU time	
		ASMO	PSO	ASMO	PSO	ASMO	PSO
Cameraman	2	12.3548	12.2519	116,195	115,195	8.0023	8.6950
	3	16.2502	14.2242	94,141,195	96,140,193	8.2679	9.1253
	4	20.0001	17.9281	40,95,141,200	76,116,151,201	8.6325	9.3562
	5	21.6002	20.0030	41,86,114,150,200	71,95,120,156,199	9.2253	10.1232
Lena	2	12.4251	12.3030	95,166	99,165	7.2154	7.8523
	3	16.3200	16.1002	87,144,190	86,151,181	7.4525	8.1254
	4	17.8282	16.9929	72,114,152,186	92,131,160,191	8.6254	9.2451
	5	20.6502	20.1253	65,94,140,161,196	75,115,145,171,198	8.9582	9.2356
Hunter	2	12.5001	12.3253	85,177	82,179	7.3251	8.0021
	3	15.7281	15.1025	59,106,177	85,128,168	8.2541	8.9582
	4	18.4152	18.0320	51,99,139,182	72,131,173,200	8.8825	9.0235
	5	20.9569	20.0209	50,96,139,178,222	90,121,166,192,219	9.7124	10.1250
Butterfly	2	10.2589	10.0021	95,144	95,142	7.1254	7.8254
	3	12.6521	12.2354	74,109.152	64,127,172	7.9696	7.9965
	4	14.9256	14.2562	70,96,128,158	71,113,164,186	8.1254	9.0001
	5	17.1205	16.8254	74,98,121,143,169	91,117,143,158,181	8.7541	9.2154
Living Room	2	12.3251	12.3000	90,172	86,176	7.1212	7.7771
	3	15.7521	15.1254	72,126,175	74,160,189	7.8963	8.1254
	4	19.1326	18.8523	60,106,150,189	58,124,172,201	8.5624	9.1253
	5	21.3562	20.8921	48,95,135,168,203	71,97,119,160,200	8.8254	9.4251

Table 3 Comparison when utilizing Otsu's objective function

Test images	n	Objective Values		Threshold value		CPU time	
		ASMO	PSO	ASMO	PSO	ASMO	PSO
Cameraman	2	3656.4825	3615.4824	72,144	73,145	3.2215	3.6002
	3	3685.6536	3675.2569	61,120,155	70,136,168	3.8215	4.1254
	4	3839.3321	3796.1254	48,106,144,172	66,123,149,174	4.4412	4.9001
	5	3870.8545	3862.2365	40,88,127,153,176	46,78,121,19,174	4.6235	5.0012
Lena	2	1978.2564	1958.9654	91,152	94,154	3.6231	3.7412
	3	2139.2563	2138.2356	77,126,172	80,129,173	3.8514	4.3216
	4	2189.7456	2180.2398	76,118,160,184	79,114,136,179	4.6891	4.9005
	5	2255.2312	2216.2356	65,93,122,160,184	78,112,142,169,188	4.9852	5.3102
Hunter	2	3202.8523	3168.2314	52,119	53,116	3.1250	3.7142
	3	3320.2389	3315.2356	37,86,139	40,88,135	3.9078	4.5120
	4	3391.2357	3267.2482	32,81,121,151	36,84,132,160	4.3692	4.9056
	5	3305.2145	3284.2584	32,75,107,141,179	35,85,127,154,180	4.8002	5.1987
Butterfly	2	1584.3692	1580.1452	98,152	97,151	3.3621	3.6253
	3	1688.3001	1668.2003	78,119,166	77,120,164	3.8523	4.3002
	4	1710.5645	1705.2450	75,105,137,169	81,115,147,177	4.6523	4.9562
	5	1736.2154	1732.2563	74,106,129,154,183	73,109,131,159,182	5.2181	5.4562
Living Room	2	1602.2104	1601.0056	87,148	90,145	2.9912	3.4561
	3	1760.1002	1756.2242	74,125,165	81,127,167	3.9002	4.1236
	4	1840.2586	1826.2323	64,102,134,170	67,108,141,178	4.0123	4.7812
	5	1870.2525	1868.2602	56,94,127,149,181	58,99,130,158,192	5.2145	5.8231

Otsu's approach is used in the second instance. Table 3 provides objective values, optimal threshold values, and CPU times when the ASMO methodology is applied to the between-class variance-based objective function (Otsu's objective function) and compared with the PSO method. The findings reveal that the segmentation quality is better and the objective values obtained using the ASMO algorithm are greater than those from the PSO approach. It is clear that when $n = 5$, the segmentation is at its best.

Tables 2 and 3 present a comparison of the computational efficiency of both methods based on the average CPU time (in seconds) needed to arrive at a solution. The outcomes show that ASMO converges more quickly than PSO methodology.

5. Conclusion

The Ageist Spider Monkey Optimization method (ASMO) is presented in this study as a solution to multi-level thresholding issues. To confirm the efficacy and efficiency of the suggested ASMO method, Otsu's approach and Kapur's method are used as the objective functions in two investigations. Using a variety of standard photos, the ASMO strategy is tried, and the outcomes are compared with the PSO method. Based on observations, the ASMO methodology performs better than the PSO method in terms of convergence speed, computational time, and appropriate threshold values. Subsequent investigations will examine the practicability of the suggested methodology and juxtapose it with alternative approaches in diverse image processing contexts.

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